

Spectrophotometric Determination of Uranium and Thorium Using Norwogonin

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Uranium(VI) and thorium(IV) form orange-coloured complexes with norwogonin (5,7,8-trihydroxyflavone). The complexes are soluble in aqueous ethanol. The use of this reagent for spectrophotometric determination of uranium and thorium has been investigated. Beer's law is obeyed over the range of 4 to 20 p.p.m. of metal ion. The thorium complex is stable between pH 2.7 and 3.9 and that of uranium, between pH 2.7 and 5.0. Solutions of the thorium complex become opalescent at or above pH 3.6 on keeping for a few hours. The molar compositions of the complexes formed by uranium and thorium have been found to be 1:2 and 1:1 respectively.

5-Hydroxyflavones are good chelating agents and many of them, such as, morin^{1,2} quercetin³, and rutin⁴, have already been investigated for spectrophotometric estimation of thorium. Morin^{3,5} and quercetin⁷ have also been used in the spectrophotometric determination of uranium. Galangin⁸, 3-methylgalangin⁹, and 5-hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxyflavone¹⁰ have been used by the authors for spectrophotometric determination of uranium and chrysin¹¹ and galangin¹² for thorium. In the present communication, the suitability of norwogonin (5,7,8-trihydroxyflavone) for spectrophotometric determination of the two metal ions has been investigated. The orange-coloured complexes of uranium(VI) and thorium(IV) with norwogonin have been studied in 40% ethanolic medium. The reagent possesses the advantages of high sensitivity and availability in a pure form; the complexes are stable over a reasonably wide acidity range.

EXPERIMENTAL

The absorption spectra in the UV region were taken, using Perkin-Elmer spectracord and for other spectrophotometric measurements, a Coleman spectrophotometer, model No. 14, was used. pH measurements were taken with a Metrohm pH meter, type

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E-350. Uranyl nitrate and thorium nitrate were used for preparing standard solutions. The solutions were standardised gravimetrically by oxine method. The reagent (norwogonin) was prepared by the method of Sastri and Seshadri¹³. A $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of the reagent was prepared for the investigations.

Complex Formation.—Uranyl and thorium ions reacted with the flavone with immediate formation of orange complexes. Complex formation was substantiated by change in colour and fall in pH.

Absorption Spectra.—Maximum absorption by the flavone was observed at 280 m μ in the UV region and at 370 m μ in the visible (Fig. 1, curve A). The absorption spectra of the complexes were studied at different pH values (2.7 to 5.0 for uranium complex and 2.7 to 3.9 for that of thorium). The absorption maximum in the case of both the complexes was found to lie at 420 m μ (Fig. 1, curves B & C). This wave length was consequently chosen for further investigations. Molar ratio of flavone to uranium or thorium was maintained at 10 during spectral studies. One ml of $M/1,000$ solution of uranyl or thorium salt was mixed with 10 ml ($M/1000$) of the flavone solution and the mixture diluted to 25.0 ml, maintaining 40% ethanolic medium. The flavone solution was used as blank and these conditions were kept constant in subsequent studies.

FIG. 1. Absorption spectra.

- A: Norwogonin using aq. EtOH as blank
 B: Uranyl-norwogonin complex using norwogonin as blank.
 C: Thorium-norwogonin complex using norwogonin as blank; pH 3.9.

Properties of the Complexes.—The complexes are soluble in aqueous ethanol and are not extractable in usual organic solvents. No change in colour was noticed on keeping the solutions for a few hours.

Effect of pH.—The effect of pH on thorium complex was studied between pH 2.7 and 3.9. Beyond pH 3.6, precipitation, however, starts on keeping the solution for a few hours. During the investigations carried out at pH 3.9, readings were taken immediately after preparing the solutions of the complex. Uranyl-norwogonin complex was found to be quite stable from pH 2.7 to 5.0. Beyond pH 5.0, the reference solution itself acquired orange colour similar to that of the complex. For pH adjustments, dilute solutions of sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid were used.

Conformity to Beer's Law.—In an attempt to draw the calibration curves for the two complexes, it was found that both the complexes adhered to Beer's law between the concentration range of 4 and 20 p.p.m. of metal ion.

FIG. 2. Job's method.

Composition of the Complexes.—The method of continued variation^{14,15} was used for determining the composition of the two complexes. Optical densities were determined in 40% ethanolic medium at wave lengths varying from 415 mμ to 430 mμ, employing norwogonin solution of the corresponding strength as reference. The results are shown in Fig. 2. From the peaks in the curves, the molar ratio of norwogonin to uranyl ion comes to 2:1 and in the case of the thorium complex, this ratio is 1:1.

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Structures of the Complexes.—Keeping in view the previous work^{3,4} and the composition of the uranyl-norwogonin complex, the following tentative structure is assigned to the complex.

In case of thorium complex, the available evidence is insufficient to enable us to assign a definite structure.

Effect of Diverse Ions.—The effect of anions like oxalate, tartrate, thiosulphate, and phosphate was studied on both the complexes. These were found to interfere even at small concentrations (7 to 8 p. p. m.), uranium or thorium concentration being of the same order as that of the ion added.

The authors' thanks are due to Prof. T. R. Seshadri, F. R. S., Head of the Chemistry Department, for his interest and encouragement and to Shri D. K. Bhardwaj for his help in the synthesis of the flavone.

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Received November 10, 1963.

Erratum

In the Feb. issue, on p. 120 in Fig. 5 read Sp. conduc $\times 10^5$ mhos for Sp. conduc. $\times 10^3$ mhos.